

Najmiddin Komilov's work as a translator and translation studies

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ABSTRACT

In this article, an accomplished literary critic, navviist, mystic, translator and translation scholar, doctor of philological sciences, professor Najmiddin Komilov, famous representatives of Eastern Sufi literature, Farididdin Attar's "Mantiq ut-tayr", "Ilohiynoma", Husain Vaiz Koshifi's "Futuvvatnomai - Sultani", Sultan Valad's "Maarif", Aziziddin Nasafi's "Zubdat ul-Haqayiq" and Sayyid Muhammad Khatami's "From the History of Islamic Thought" translated from Persian into Uzbek by skillful translation, in general, scientific study and assessment of the scientist's translation activities, and the scientist's current problems of translation studies. His views on research are analyzed. The above-mentioned translator Najmiddin Komilov's works, translated from Persian to Uzbek, have a fluent language and a simple style, and the reader will have no difficulty in reading the translated work. In the article, the translator's "Translation skills of Muhammad Reza Ogahi" (candidacy thesis), "Khorazm school of translation (problems of typological and comparative research of the translation history of the 19th century)" (doctoral thesis), "This is an ancient art", "Caravans of thought" and the co-authored scientific research "Bridges of Friendship" and "Translator's Skills" were analyzed, about 20 literary translations from Persian by the famous poet, historian and translator M.R. Ogahi, Ogahi's translation skills, which stand in a high position in Uzbek translation studies. The emergence, formation and development of Khorezm translation school, prominent representatives of Khorezm translation school.

artistic translation and its poetic and prose forms, complex aspects and requirements of poetic translation, the importance of translation in studying the work of Hafiz and Goethe and other thinker poets of classical Eastern and Western literature, in general, N. Komilov's Uzbek translation studies Scientific opinions and views on current problems were studied. While referring to the history of Uzbek translation studies, translator Najmiddin Komilov provides information about the translation work of Abu Rayhan Beruni, a great encyclopedist, a representative of Eastern Renaissance culture, who made a great contribution to the development of the Khorezm translation school. According to the translator, A. Beruni knew several languages such as Arabic (Syriac), Greek, Indian (Sanskrit), Jewish (Hebrew), Persian and Turkish and was recognized as a skilled translator and a clever translator of his time. The studies of the hard-working scientist on the development of Uzbek translation studies are distinguished by their richness in literary-aesthetic, philosophical-logical thinking. In the conditions of today's globalization, translation and translation studies have an important role in the development of science in Uzbekistan, since translations lead humanity to progress and raise world civilization.

During the years of independence in Uzbekistan, national-spiritual revival was defined as the priority direction of state policy, and special attention was paid to the issues of national identity, restoration of national-spiritual and religious values. The services of eminent scientist, doctor of philology, professor Najmiddin Kamilov in studying the rich material and spiritual heritage created by our ancestors, which contributed to the development of world civilization over the centuries, are very important for these reforms in all fields of science in our country, including literary studies (history of classic literature, navai studies), mysticism and translation studies. huge Zaki scientist Najmiddin Komilov devoted his life to the fields of science, education, management, religion and mysticism of our country. N.Komilov took an active part in the spiritual reforms taking place in our country as a dedicated scientist with his articles on national identity awareness, national spirituality and religious values. N.Komilov's scientific activity is diverse, and the scientific views of the scientist in his studies of literature, linguistics, philosophy, history, religious studies, political science, ethics, aesthetics, psychology, management (oriental management), mysticism, and translation studies are recognized by world scientists. In particular, the scientist's views on the theoretical issues of literary studies such as classical literary history, comparative literary studies, translation studies and history of translation, textual studies, navoi studies, as well as Eastern and Western literary relations, Sufism literature, rich in deep educational and literary observations, researches on current topics are his advanced philosophy and scientific

knowledge. is distinguished by In particular, the scholar's work as a translator and translation studies deserves special recognition. Speaking about the scholar's work as a translator and translation studies, it is worth noting that the teacher knew the Persian-Tajik and Russian languages well.

Our opinion is based on the well-known representatives of Eastern Sufism literature, Farididdin Attar's "Mantiq ut - Tayr", "Ilohiynama", "Futuvvatnamai - Sultani" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, "Maarif" by Sultan Valad, "Zubdat ul - Haqayiq" by Aziziddin Nasafi and Sayyid Muhammad Khatami. The fluent language and simple style of his skillful translations of the works from the "History of Islamic Thought" from Persian to Uzbek prove it. It is known that the language and style of these works, which are products of medieval Persian-Tajik mystical literature, are complex and require great knowledge and experience from this translator. Translations from Persian to Uzbek by skilled translator Najmiddin Komilov do not cause difficulties for the reader, the language and style are fluent. We can clearly see this in the example of Najmiddin Komilov's prose translation, interpretation, and interpretation of Attar Nishopuri's work "Ilohiynama" by Sheikh Ibrahim Muhammad Farididdin, one of the great figures of Eastern literature, one of the great mystics. The translator translated a part of Farididdin Attar's work "Ilohiinoma" written in masnavi, "Story of Sheikh San'an" from the epic "Mantiq ut-Tayr" and several stories from Persian to Uzbek in the form of prose stories. in the language, the changes in the compact form were made on the basis of the content and form proportionality.

Also, "Translation skills of Muhammad Reza Ogahi" (candidacy thesis), "Khorazm school of translation (problems of typological and comparative research of translation history of the 19th century)" (doctoral thesis), "This is an ancient art", "Tafkkur" Caravans" and the scientific research "Dostlik prikriklari" and "Translator's skill" created in co-authorship are significant because they are dedicated to the most relevant topics of translation. In these studies, about 20 literary translations from the Persian language of the famous poet, historian and translator M.R. Ogahi, Ogahi's translation skills, the emergence, formation and development of the Khorezm translation school, which stands at a high position in Uzbek translation studies, the bright representatives of the Khorezm translation school, artistic translation and its poetic and prose forms, the complex aspects and requirements of poetic translation, the importance of translation in studying the works of Hafiz and Goethe and other thinkers of classical Eastern and Western literature, scientific opinion about the current problems of Uzbek translation studies in general and views have been studied.

While referring to the history of Uzbek translation studies, translator Najmiddin Komilov provides information about the translation work of Abu Rayhan Beruni, a great encyclopedist, a representative of Eastern Renaissance culture, who made a great contribution to the development of the Khorezm translation school. According to the translator, A. Beruni knew several languages such as Arabic (Syriac), Greek, Indian (Sanskrit), Jewish (Hebrew), Persian and Turkish and was recognized as a skilled translator and a clever translator of his time. It is clear that the emergence and development of the Eastern Renaissance culture of Central Asia has a great contribution of translators and scholars who worked in "Bayt ul-Hikma" established first in Baghdad and later in Khorazm (Khorazm Ma'mun Academy). The studies of the hard-working scientist on the development of Uzbek translation studies are distinguished by their richness in literary-aesthetic, philosophical-logical thinking. In the conditions of today's globalization, translation and translation studies have an important role in the development of science in Uzbekistan, since translations lead humanity to progress and raise world civilization.

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